

INVESTIGATION OF COMPRESSIVE FAILURE IN ULTRA-HIGH MOLECULAR WEIGHT POLYETHYLENE (DYNEEMA[®]) FIBRE COMPOSITES

J.P. Attwood^{1*}, V.S. Deshpande¹, N.A. Fleck¹

¹ Department of Engineering, University of Cambridge, Trumpington Street, Cambridge, CB2 1PZ, UK

* Corresponding author (<mailto:jpa38@cam.ac.uk>)

Keywords: *UHMWPE composite, ballistic, compression, microbuckling*

1 Introduction

The threats faced by military and law enforcement personnel are evolving every day. In order to offer them the best protection possible, the strategies and materials used for ballistic protection must also evolve.

Dyneema[®] is an ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) fibre composite currently used for ballistic protection, among other applications. The composite material considered here, HB26, is a grade of Dyneema[®] laminate manufactured by DSM Dyneema. The grade contains SK76 fibres arranged in a 0/90 stacking sequence, as shown in Figure 1. HB26 uses a stiff polyurethane matrix, as opposed to various other DSM grades, which use a softer krayton rubber matrix. The relevant mechanical properties for HB26 are shown in Table 1.

The use of Dyneema[®] as an impact resistance system offers improvements through its low density and improved ballistic properties with respect to CFRP [11]. The material has a density lower than water [17], allowing it to float, giving obvious benefits when considering the varied conditions military personnel experience.

However, in order to determine how best to use Dyneema[®], and how to continue to improve it, a solid understanding of its material and mechanical properties must be obtained. Various studies of the individual properties of the fibres and matrix have been carried out, as discussed in section 2, but further work is necessary to fully understand the interaction between these components, and the failure mechanisms of the laminate as a whole. The paper presented here seeks to delve further into the modes of failure, and explain one of the fundamental mechanisms at work.

2 Literature review

Dyneema[®] has excellent specific properties[4][20] and has shown promise in ballistic resistance applications[11], leading to an interest in its mechanisms of failure.

The fibres, independent of the matrix, have been studied by van Dingenen (1989) [20] and shown to be a very versatile material. After this overview paper, several researchers began to look at the fibre properties in more depth. Berger et al (2003)[2] studied the fibre microstructure's response to creep, developing models based on both fibrillar and crystalline structures, and deduced that care in manufacturing and protection from damage were key to performance. Govaert and Peijs (1995) [7] found a dependence of tensile strength of the fibres on both strain rate and temperature, and Hazell et al (2011) [10] determined that shock wave propagation in the material can be halted by fibres melting on contact with the wave.

UHMWPE laminates have been studied mostly to determine the effects of different methods of manufacturing on the mechanical properties. Marais and Feillard (1992) [13] used a hot compaction route to produce a material with high crystallinity and highly anisotropic behavior, while Morye et al (1999) [15] compared this hot compaction route to laying up pre-pregs into a mould.

Marissen (2011) [14] wrote a review of the material's applications, including biomedical, fabric and personal protection.

As research began to progress to laminates, the lack of understanding of Dyneema[®]'s unique properties meant that other composites were often considered, in order to suggest mechanisms on which to base models. Dyneema[®] has been compared to cured and uncured carbon fibre, in Karthikeyan et al

(2013)[11]. Kevlar is an obvious choice for comparison for a material showing good ballistic properties. It was characterized well by Greenwood and Rose (1974)[9] and was shown to be dependent on fibre strength for its ballistic properties. Padmanabhan (1995)[16] confirmed this by studying the interlaminar shear strength in Kevlar composites. Composites containing both Kevlar and Dyneema[®] fibres have also been suggested and modeled [9].

CFRP is a well characterized material, and often a point of reference for composite tests. Microbuckling has been studied in carbon composites, with notched compression tests performed by Soutis et al (1993)[19], Fleck et al (1995)[5] and Sivashanker et al (1996)[18]. Soutis et al (1993)[19] considered various lay-ups and concluded that fibre microbuckling was the dominant microbuckling mechanism for CFRP in the UD and multi-directional states. Fleck et al (1995) [5] considered a single stacking sequence [+45,-45,0,0], but compared it to woven laminates, and to microbuckling in plywood, and found plastic microbuckling to be the critical mechanism. Sivashanker et al (1996)[18] used a crack bridging model to examine the propagation of the kink band through a UD carbon fibre laminate. This was the study which was followed most closely for the microbuckling experiments which were carried out for this paper. A very comprehensive microbuckling text is a review paper by Fleck (1997)[6], which discusses the mechanisms involved in the initiation, propagation and growth of microbuckles in fibre composites. Dyneema[®], however, had not previously been studied in this mode.

Ballistic testing of UHMWPE composites is a fairly recent subject of research in the area. Cheeseman and Bogetti (2003) [3] tested Dyneema[®] fabrics and discussed the energy dissipation mechanisms. Leigh Phoenix et al (2010) [12] developed a model for various stacking sequences of a Dyneema[®]/Kevlar composite. Russell et al (2013) [17] measured the strain rate dependency in tension of a variety of Dyneema[®] materials, fibres, yarns and laminates, while Karthikeyan et al [11] considered the effect of shear strength on ballistic performance.

The damage to composite plates in ballistic tests has been shown to be very complex, involving various failure modes, as shown in Greenhalgh et al, (2012)

[8]. An example of a Dyneema[®] plate that has been subjected to a ballistic impact is given in Figure 2, showing the resulting damage. It is this unique and complicated problem that must now be addressed by researchers.

3. Motivation

Figure 2 clearly shows that the complexity and variety of mechanisms in the failure of Dyneema[®] composites will make them very difficult to model, or to quantitatively understand. A more straightforward means of analyzing the mechanisms was sought, by exploring how these failure modes could be reliably reproduced separately, to allow for a simpler model.

Quasi-static tests were used as a means of studying each facet of the failure in a more controlled, straightforward environment. They also reproduced the damage seen in ballistic tests very well, providing reassurance that the same failure mechanisms were at work. Karthikeyan et al [11] showed the progressive ply failure of HB26 in ballistic tests of increasing velocity. This can be compared to Figure 3, which shows an x-ray computer tomography (XCT) image of a plate indented with a punch of similar dimensions to the projectile used in the ballistic tests from [11]. The obvious similarities between the failed specimens, i.e. the progressive ply failure under the punch, indicates that quasi-static testing is a viable option for studying the individual failure mechanisms at work in Dyneema[®].

4. Microbuckling study

One of the failure mechanisms visible in Figure 2 is microbuckling, or 'kinking', where the material has experienced shear and in-plane compression as a result of ballistic impact. This failure mode can be investigated through notched compression tests similar to those undertaken by Sivashanker et al (1996)[18]. The in-plane compression of HB26 was analyzed and the mechanisms responsible for failure identified.

4.1 Experimental method

Notched samples were cut from HB26 laminate with a thickness of 6 mm. The material was cut using a 0.5 mm thick bandsaw, with the composite clamped between sheets of wood to prevent delamination

along the edges. The samples were 30 mm in width, 60 mm in height and included a notch with root diameter of 2 mm and opening length of 6 mm as shown in Figure 4. The notch was formed by drilling a 2 mm diameter hole into the material and cutting away the material to the edges. The root of the notch was then sliced with a razor blade in order to give a more pronounced stress concentration.

Small nylon blocks were machined to slide onto the top and bottom of the samples to prevent brooming of the composite during loading. These were machined to be slightly too large for the samples, so as to prevent damage to the sample when fitting. In order to provide a close fit, slips of paper were folded over the top and bottom of the sample to increase the thickness at that point.

Vertical lines were drawn on the front surface of the pristine specimens to allow the progression of the microbuckle to be more easily seen. Lines were marked at 2 mm intervals from the root of the notch to the edge of the sample.

A clip gauge with 5 mm of total travel and a gauge length of 20 mm was attached to the front face of the sample in order to measure remote displacement. The clip gauge had small, razor-ended attachments fitted to the arms, which were positioned 20 mm from the top and bottom edge of the sample on one of the 'front' faces. Elastic bands were wrapped around the sample and the clip gauge arm attachments in order to maintain the position of the attachments. Care was taken not to damage the sample with the razor edges by ensuring that the elastic bands were loose enough to prevent the clip gauge from cutting the surface of the specimen.

The samples were tested using a screw-driven Instron tensometer, at a displacement rate of 0.5 mm/min. Measurements of displacement of the crosshead and load applied to the sample were recorded by the machine and exported as a .csv file. The clip gauge readings were also stored and exported by the machine. This data was then used to calculate the remote stress applied to the sample. Accurate measurements of the width and thickness of the samples were taken prior to testing to ensure the accuracy of the stress measurements.

The specimens were analyzed using an X-Tek XCT scanner, obtaining 360 images at 40 kV and 50 μ A,

as for Figure 3. This allowed the internal damage to be viewed, showing delamination through the centre of the material. Images were also obtained using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) to examine the damage visible to the plies at the edges of samples.

4.2 Results and Observations

The peak stress for microbuckling of HB26 was found to be 12 MPa, as shown in the stress vs displacement curve in Figure 5. There is very little displacement until the onset of microbuckling, at which point the stress drops and the sample deforms at a new, approximately constant, stress. The second peak represents the formation of a new microbuckle at a secondary location, once the microbuckle has traveled the entire width of the sample and reached its maximum vertical displacement. Once formed, the microbuckle propagated across the sample quickly, forming a fine line of damage. The microbuckle was visible from both sides of the specimen, as the material deformed across its entire thickness.

Figure 6 shows the progression of failure, and the stages the damage moves through, from a side view of the sample. The initial stage involves shearing of the matrix between the plies, creating a band of misaligned fibres across the sample and causing delamination between the plies. This band is inclined at approximately 30° from the horizontal and resembles a shear band. As the applied displacement continues, the plies rotate further and the fibres within them develop kinks. This allows the fibres to shorten, and accommodate the continuing rotation.

Once the fibres have shortened to their maximum extent, in other words, once they are perpendicular to the inclination of the shear band, the band begins to broaden, in an effort to dissipate strain energy and allow rotation of the plies to continue. When the plies reach a rotation of 90° to their starting orientation, lock-up occurs and the microbuckle halts its growth. At this point, a 'secondary' microbuckle must form in another location if the load continues to be applied.

This microbuckling mode displays the behavior of several different types of typical microbuckles, such as shear banding and plastic microbuckling.

Images of the side of a failed sample, with loading stopped just after the initial peak, (with the sample rotated 90° compared to those in Figure 6 above) were taken using an SEM, and examined for signs of the mechanisms described. One of the SEM images is shown in Figure 7. This image clearly shows the rotation of the plies, and the edge of the shear band, where the fibres must shorten to accommodate the change in orientation.

Both the 0° and 90° fibres can be seen here, but the fibres out of plane have been smeared by cutting during sample preparation, and appeared much thicker. This effect is more visible in Figure 8, where the edges of the fibres are shown to be an irregular shape. Layers of 0° and 90° fibres are in fact approximately the same thickness. This figure also shows the delamination and matrix bridging present in the shear band. This is a result of the shearing of the matrix during compression. The plies have rotated significantly, and have reached the point where band broadening would begin to occur.

At the ‘corners’ of the band, fibre shortening is visible. There is no indication that fibres have been broken, but there are areas of buckling damage lined up along the change in direction of the fibres. This is shown in Figure 9, where the direction of viewing has changed from an edge on view, as in Figure 6, to a front view, as described in Figure 4. This shows only the 0° plies. The kinks in the fibres can be seen to follow a path across the material, along the ‘peak’ of the microbuckle. Similar kinking is seen along the ‘trough’.

4.3 Discussion and Validation

Comparing the peak stress for microbuckling to the failure strength of an HB26 laminate (given in Table 1), along with the observations made during failure, it is clear that failure is dominated by the matrix properties, rather than that of the fibres. However, in order to confirm this, tensile recoil tests, as devised by Allen (1987)[1] were undertaken to find the compressive stress required to kink, or shorten the fibres.

Single SK76 fibres were selected from a yarn, taking care not to damage the fibre, and a weight of known value was hung from it. The ends of the fibres were glued to paper tabs, to which the weights were then

taped. These tabs were weighed at the end of testing and the added weight was found to be negligible.

This induced a known tensile force in the fibre. The fibre was then sliced cleanly with a razor blade, causing a compressive wave to move through the remaining half of the fibre. When a kink in the fibre was first identified, the force caused by the weight was taken to be the threshold value for the kinking force. A ‘true’ kink, for compressive failure, was considered to be one found well away from the support, as the magnitude of the wave is doubled here due to reflection at the support.

For SK76 Dyneema® fibres, the corresponding stress was found to be 362 MPa, well above the microbuckling stress for the HB26 composite (12 MPa). Thus the microbuckling mode is dominated by the strength of the matrix in shear, with fibre kinking caused by ply rotation.

5. Discussion

5.1 Conclusions

The microbuckling strength of HB26 has been found to be 12 MPa. Microbuckles form through a combination of mechanisms, beginning with shear banding, which leads to ply rotation, requiring fibre kinking and band broadening. The kinking (compressive) strength of the fibres has been identified as 362 MPa from tensile recoil tests[1].

This combination of modes has not been recorded in a fibre composite, therefore the study presented here introduces a new microbuckling mode unique to Dyneema®.

This knowledge of the mechanics of the material may help to better understand the ballistic performance of Dyneema®, by providing a value for a mechanical property, the in-plane compressive strength (12 MPa), and by isolating and analyzing one of the failure mechanisms at work.

5.2 Significance with regards to ballistic testing

By identifying the separate failure mechanisms involved in the ballistic failure of Dyneema® composites, each one can be explored in more straightforward systems. These studies, in turn provide valuable data on the mechanics of the mode, which can be fed back in to ballistic models.

The study presented here has provided a better understanding of the compressive strength of the material, of the damage occurring during ballistic tests and, more specifically, of the microbuckles which form away from the point of impact.

Clearly the interaction of these mechanisms must be investigated to fully understand ballistic failure, but they can be used to suggest means by which the composite could be improved.

An increase in the stiffness of the matrix could provide benefits to the microbuckling strength, preventing damage from spreading through plates and allowing armour to remain more intact, improving resistance to multiple hits.

6. Further work

Various other mechanisms are at play in the ballistic failure of Dyneema®, such as fibre fracture, uniform compression under the projectile, and delamination. These mechanisms should be studied in more detail and related to the ballistic tests. Work has already begun to link uniform compression tests to the ballistic tests performed by Karthikeyan et al[11].

The cross-ply [0/90] arrangement is the most commonly studied Dyneema® laminate, but other stacking sequences could provide benefits to the ballistic properties and should be investigated.

Modelling of the material is underway [12], but the validation of the various methods must be performed, by altering some of the properties of the laminates in testing and comparing to model predictions.

Dyneema® remains a complex and challenging material to understand, but also an excellent prospect in the ballistic protection industry. Further study of its fundamental properties will lead to a more solid understanding of its behavior and the confidence to design for future needs.

7. Acknowledgements

The authors are grateful to DSM Dyneema for providing the HB26 laminate materials for this study, and for the technical discussions which helped to develop the research. Dyneema® is a trademark of DSM. The authors are also grateful for the support provided by the funded DARPA Soldier Protection Systems project. J. P Attwood is grateful

to the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council for their financial support.

Figures

Fig. 1. An example of the 0/90 stacking sequence of HB26.

Grade	Ply thickness (µm)	Tensile strength σ_t (MPa)	Shear strength τ_o (MPa)
HB26	60	1600	2

Table 1. Mechanical properties for laminates of HB26, all values from [11].

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Fig. 2. Sample of HB26 which has been subjected to a ballistic impact showing, (a) impact face at 450 m/s (b)

close-up of damage showing microbuckling and broken fibres (c) back face severely deflected (d) side view showing deflection of back face with no penetration.

Fig. 3. Progressive ply failure of HB26 in a quasi-static indentation test using a flat-bottomed punch.

Fig. 4. Diagram of the specimen geometry used for notched compression testing.

Fig. 5. Plot of remote stress against remote displacement for microbuckling of an HB26 sample.

Fig. 6. Diagram showing the key stages in the development of the microbuckle in HB26 from a side view

Fig. 7. SEM image of the side edge of a failed sample, showing shear banding and rotation of the plies.

Fig. 8. SEM image near the edge of the sample, with the smearing of out of plane fibres more visible, and a band of delamination shown.

Fig. 9. SEM image showing kinks in the fibres, allowing them to shorten, along the shear band edge.

References

- [1] S.R. Allen “Tensile recoil measurement of compressive strength for polymeric high performance fibres” *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol. 22, pp 853-859, 1987.
- [2] L. Berger, H. Kausch, and C. Plummer “Structure and deformation mechanisms in UHMWPE-fibres”. *Polymer*, Vol. 44, No. 19, pp 5877 – 5884, 2003.
- [3] B.A. Cheeseman and T.A. Bogetti “Ballistic impact into fabric and compliant composite laminates” *Composite Structures*, Vol. 61, pp 161-173, 2003.
- [4] M. Deng and S.W. Shalaby “Properties of self-reinforced ultra-high-molecular-weight polyethylene composites”. *Biomaterials*, Vol. 18, No. 9, pp 645-655, 1997.
- [5] N.A. Fleck, P.M. Jelf, and P.T. Curtis “Compressive failure of laminated and woven composites” *Journal of Composites Technology and Research*, Vol. 17, No. 3, pp 212-220, 1995.
- [6] N.A. Fleck “Compressive failure of fiber composites”, *Advances in Applied Mechanics*, Vol. 33, pp 43-113, 1997.
- [7] L. Govaert, and T. Peijs “Tensile strength and work of fracture of oriented polyethylene fibre”. *Polymer*, Vol. 36, No. 23, pp 4425-4431, 1995.
- [8] E.S. Greenhalgh, V.M. Bloodworth, L. Iannucci and D. Pope “Fractographic observations on Dyneema® composites under ballistic impact”. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, Vol. 44, pp 51-62, 2013.
- [9] J.H. Greenwood and P.G. Rose “Compressive behavior of Kevlar 49 fibres and composites” *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol. 9, pp 1809-1814, 1974.
- [10] P.J. Hazell, G.J. Appleby-Thomas, X. Trinquant and D.J. Chapman “In-fiber shock propagation in Dyneema®” *Journal of Applied Physics*, Vol. 110, No. 4, pp 043504-1 – 043504-5.
- [11] Karthikeyan K., B.P. Russell, N.A. Fleck, H.N.G. Wadley and V.S. Deshpande “The effect of shear strength on the impact response of laminated composite plates”. *European Journal of Solid Mechanics A* (accepted manuscript) 2013.
- [12] S. Leigh Phoenix, A. Kadir Yavuz and P.K. Porwal “New interference approach for ballistic impact into stacked flexible composite body armor” *AIAA Journal*, Vol. 48, No. 2, pp 490-501, 2010.
- [13] C. Marais and P. Feillard “Manufacturing and mechanical characterization of unidirectional composites”. *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 45, pp 247-255, 1992.
- [14] R. Marissen “Design with ultra strong polyethylene fibers” *Materials Sciences and Applications*, Vol 2, No. 5, pp 319-330, 2011.
- [15] S.S. Morye, P.J. Hine, R.A. Duckett, D.J. Carr and I.M. Ward “A comparison of the properties of hot compacted gel-spun polyethylene fibre composites with conventional gel-spun polyethylene fibre composites”. *Composites Part A: applied science and manufacturing*, Vol. 30, pp 649-660, 1999.
- [16] K. Padmanabhan, Kishore “Interlaminar shear of woven fabric Kevlar-epoxy composites in three-point loading” *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, Vol. 197, No. 1, pp 113-118, 1995.
- [17] B.P. Russell, K. Karthikeyan, V.S. Deshpande and N.A. Fleck “The high strain rate response of ultra high molecular-weight polyethylene: from fibre to laminate”. *International Journal of Impact Engineering* (accepted manuscript), 2013.
- [18] S. Sivashanker, N.A. Fleck, and M.P.F. Sutcliffe “Microbuckle propagation in a unidirectional carbon fibre-epoxy matrix composite”. *Acta Materialis*, Vol. 44, No. 7, pp 2581-2590, 1996.
- [19] C. Soutis, P.T. Curtis and N.A. Fleck “Compressive failure of notched carbon fibre composites” *Proceedings of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, Vol. 440, No. 1909, pp 241-256, 1993.
- [20] J. van Dingenen “High performance Dyneema fibres in composites”. *Materials & Design*, Vol. 10, No. 2, pp 101 – 104, 1989.